

Influence of Cement and Sand Replacement on Strength Properties of High-Volume Fly Ash Concrete

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Abstract:

Fly ash, a waste product from coal combustion in thermal power plants, can be effectively reused in concrete to reduce disposal issues and construction costs. This study investigates the partial replacement of cement (40%, 50%, 60%) and sand (50%–90%) in a 1:1.5:3 concrete mix. Results show a decrease in compressive strength with higher fly ash content, making it suitable for low-load structural applications. Economic analysis was also conducted for the fly ash concrete mixes.

Keywords : Fly ash, Compressive Strength, Bulk Density, Mix proportion.

1. Introduction :

Coal ash, a by-product of coal combustion in thermal power plants, is mainly classified into fly ash and bottom ash, with fly ash widely used in the construction industry due to its low cost and beneficial properties. Fly ash serves as a partial replacement for cement and sand in concrete, enhancing workability, impermeability, and resistance to sulphate attacks. Mortar, although comprising only 7% of masonry walls, plays a critical structural role, prompting ongoing research into incorporating waste materials like fly ash to reduce environmental impact and construction costs. As the production of Portland cement emits significant carbon dioxide and consumes considerable energy and money, replacing up to 40% of cementitious materials with fly ash and lime offers an effective, eco-friendly alternative. Consequently, the use of fly ash in concrete is increasingly favored to improve strength while minimizing costs and environmental harm.

2. Materials used:

For the preparation of the high volume flyash concrete, following materials are used:

2.1 OPC of grade-43- Used Ramco Cement of Grade-43

Table 2.1.1 Physical Properties of cement

Test Particulars	Results Obtained	Requirements of IS:8112-2013
Fineness (m ² /KG)	308	Minimum 225
Normal Consistency (%)	27.86	
Initial Setting Time (Minutes)	153	Minimum 30
Final Setting Time (Minutes)	256	Maximum 600
Le-Chatlier Expansion (mm) Soundness	1	Maximum 10
Autoclave Expansion (%) Soundness	0.02	Maximum 0.80
Compressive Strength (MPa)- 72 +/- 1 Hrs (3 Days)	34.1	Minimum 23
Compressive Strength (MPa)- 168 +/- 2 Hrs (7 Days)	43.5	Minimum 33

Table 2.1.2 Chemical Properties of cement

Test Particulars	Results Obtained	Requirements of IS:8112-2013
CaO % - 0.7 SO ₃ % /2.8 SiO ₂ % + 1.2 Al ₂ O ₃ %+ 0.65 Fe ₂ O ₃ %	0.91	0.66 to 1.02
% Al ₂ O ₃ / % Fe ₂ O ₃	1.41	Minimum 0.66
Insoluble Residue (% by Mass)	0.77	Maximum 4.0
Magnesia (% by Mass)	1.17	Maximum 6.0
Sulphuric Anhydride (% by Mass)	2.04	Maximum 3.5
Total Loss on Ignition (% by Mass)	2.87	Maximum 5.0
Chloride Content (% by Mass)	0.012	Maximum 0.10
Tricalcium Aluminate (C ₃ A)	8.11	

2.2 Fly Ash

As we know that this by-product is generated from thermal power plants. So, we contacted the nearest thermal power plant of N.T.P.C. It belongs to Government of India and which is situated in Angul, which is about 120 km from the institution. The physical and chemical properties are further studied at IIT ,bhubaneswar and the following result is found. In case of chemical analysis 2 sample of same Fly Ash is taken for more accuracy. The physical and chemical properties is given in tables below.

Table 2.2.1 Physical properties of Fly Ash

LOI	Density(g/cc)	Blain Area(m ² /kg)
	2.1	350

Table 2.2.2 Chemical properties of Fly Ash

Type of Fly Ash	Test Parameters(%)				
	Fe ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO
1	5.17	60.13	30.85	0.76	0.45
2	3.98	55.08	27.96	0.65	0.41

2.3. Fine Aggregate

Natural sand which is collected from the local river is of maximum size 4.5mm was used as fine aggregate for the study. The physical and sieve analysis of above fine aggregate are presented in table below.

Table No. 2.3.1 Physical Properties of Fine Aggregate

Sl. No.	Properties	Studied Values
1	Bulk Density(Kg/m ³)	1652
2	Specific Gravity	2.7

3	Water Absorption %	0.73
4	Fineness Modulus	2.39
5	Abrasion Value	14.6 %

Weight of sample taken = 500 grams

Table No. 2.3.2 Sieve Analysis of Fine Aggregate

I.S.Sieve size in mm	Weight retained in gms	% Weight retained in gms	Cumulative % of weight retained	% Passing	Requirement for Zone-III as per IS:383-1970
10	0	0	0	100	100
4.75	8.8	1.77	1.8	98.23	90-100
2.36	44.7	8.93	10.7	89.3	85-100
1.18	38.5	7.7	18.4	81.6	75-100
0.6	76	15.2	33.6	66.4	60-79
0.3	189	37.8	71.4	28.6	12-40
0.15	112	22.4	93.8	6.2	0-10

The above Fine aggregate sample conforms to grading Zone-III of IS: 383-1970

Sl. No.	Properties	Observed Value
1	Bulk Density(Kg/m ³)	1698
2	Specific Gravity	2.83
3	Water Absorption%	0.2
4	Fineness Modules	6.47
5	Abrasion Value%	18.6
6	Impact Value%	15.3

2.4. Coarse Aggregate

Black hard coarse crusher broken natural stone aggregates with maximum 20mm size are used in this study. The aggregate are tested as per IS:383-1970. Different test results are mentioned in table below.

Table No.2.4.1. Sieve Analysis of Coarse Aggregate

Weight of sample taken = 5000 grams

Table No. 2.4.2. Nominal size of Coarse Aggregates

I.S. Sieve size in mm	Weight retained in grams	%weight retained in grams	Cumulative % of weight retained	%Passing	Requirement as per IS: 383-1970
40	0	0	0	100	100
20	135	2.7	2.7	97.3	95-100
10	2440	48.8	51.5	48.5	25-55
4.75	2110	42.2	93.7	6.3	0-10

The coarse aggregate sample conforms to 20 mm graded aggregates of nominal size as per table 2 of IS: 383:1970.

Fig: Determination of Specific Gravity and abrasion value of CA.

Fig : Proportioning of Materials.

2.5. Water

Normal portable drinking water from GIFT Laboratory was used for all the work in this work. Water used was tested as per the requirements of IS:456-2000. The test results were obtained from SM Consultants, Bhubaneswar are presented in table no. 2.5.1

Table 2.5.1 Properties of Water

Sl No	Properties	Observed Value
1	pH value	7.1
2	Dissolved Solid(mg/l)	290
3	Suspended Solids	Nil
4	Chlorides(mg/l)	20
5	Sulphates(mg/l)	74
6	MPN Value/100	Nil

3. Methodology

3.1. Specimen Preparation

In order to make the mix uniform and to get the mix well mixed up we have followed the following procedure-

Sieve Analysis- For Fly Ash we used 75 μ of sieve and sieved the total amount of Fly Ash which is required in kg. Then, coarse aggregate is sieved. Coarse aggregate is taken in 2 different size by sieve analysis. Both are taken 50%. First one is taken with 20mm passed and 4.5 mm retain , then the second one is taken as 12mm pass and 4.5 mm retained.

Similarly, According to the above table the materials are taken in kilogram/meter cube and then place in three different trays.

Figure-3.1.1- Concrete specimens in different proportions.

Quantity of materials used for the preparation of the mix.

Replacement(%)	Cement (Kg/m ³)	Flyash (Kg/m ³)	Sand(Kg/m ³)	Coarse aggregate (Kg/m ³)	Water %
40 cement	252.12	168.08	630.3	1260.6	0.45
50 cement	210.1	210.1	630.3	1260.6	0.45
60 cement	168.08	252.12	630.3	1260.6	0.45
40 cement - 50 sand	252.12	483.23	315.15	1260.6	0.45
50 cement - 50 sand	210.1	625.25	315.15	1260.6	0.45
60 cement - 50 sand	168.08	567.27	315.15	1260.6	0.45
40 cement - 60 sand	252.12	420.2	252.12	1260.6	0.45
50 cement - 60 sand	210.1	462.22	252.12	1260.6	0.45
60 cement - 60 sand	168.08	504.24	252.12	1260.6	0.45
40 cement - 70 sand	252.12	357.17	189.09	1260.6	0.45
50 cement - 70 sand	210.1	399.19	189.09	1260.6	0.45
60 cement - 70 sand	168.08	441.21	189.09	1260.6	0.45
40 cement - 80 sand	252.12	294.14	126.06	1260.6	0.45
50 cement - 80 sand	210.1	336.16	126.06	1260.6	0.45
60 cement - 80 sand	168.08	378.18	126.06	1260.6	0.45
40 cement - 90 sand	252.12	231.11	63.03	1260.6	0.45
50 cement - 90 sand	210.1	273.13	63.03	1260.6	0.45
60 cement - 90 sand	168.08	315.15	63.03	1260.6	0.45

Table 3.1.1- Materials Used in Kg/m³

3.2. Compressive strength Testing

For the above studies we have decided to find the compressive strength of the hardened cubes. That's why to find the compressive strength of the cube we used the Compressive Test Machine which available in our laboratory.

Figure 3.2.1. Compressive Strength Test Of Cube in Compression Testing Machine

4. Results and Discussion

Graph 4.1 - Compressive Strength of cement replaced concrete with Fly Ash

Graph 4.2- Compressive Strength of Concrete by replacement of Cement and 50% sand with Fly Ash

Graph 4.3- Compressive Strength of Concrete by replacement of Cement and 60% sand with Fly Ash.

Graph 4.4 - Compressive Strength of Concrete by replacement of Cement and 70% sand with Fly Ash

Graph 4.5- Compressive Strength of Concrete by replacement of Cement and 80% sand with Fly Ash

Graph 4.6- Compressive Strength of Concrete by replacement of Cement and 90% sand with Fly Ash.

5. Conclusion :

The experimental results show that fly ash can effectively replace both cement and sand in concrete. When cement was replaced by 40%, 50%, and 60%, the compressive strengths were 35.69 MPa, 41.83 MPa, and 25.8 MPa respectively, with 50% replacement yielding the highest strength. For 40% cement and varying sand replacements (50–90%), all samples exceeded 20 MPa, with the highest strength of 28.44 MPa at 50% sand replacement. With 50% cement, sand replacements of 50%, 70%, and 80% also gave strengths above 20 MPa, peaking at 27.14 MPa. At 60% cement replacement, only the mix with 50% sand replacement exceeded 20 MPa, achieving 21.3 MPa.

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